

**MGG / PRODIGEES
Final Conference Report**

*Digitalisation Towards
Sustainable Development*

MEXICO
CITY

9-13

MARCH
2025

From March 9 to 12, 2025, more than 70 researchers, policymakers, and practitioners from 8 different countries across 5 continents came together to reflect on and discuss pressing questions of digitalisation and sustainable development. The **MGG/PRODIGEES Final Conference** was the concluding event of Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development (PRODIGEES), a five-year project funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 MSCA-RISE programme. Embedded in the Managing Global Governance (MGG) network of the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) and co-lead by IDOS and Instituto Mora (Mexico), the project facilitated comparative, transnational research on the intersection of digitalisation with governance, society, economy, and environment across Europe, Brazil, India, Indonesia, Mexico, and South Africa. The regions are facing distinct but interconnected challenges in balancing digital transformation with sustainable development.

The event provided a platform for participating researchers to present the project's publications, policy recommendations, future action plans, and training initiatives. The event also engaged a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, academic institutions, civil society, and the general public to disseminate project results.

The conference opened with welcome remarks by Dr. Carlos Dominguez Virgen (Mora), Dr. Wulf Reiners (IDOS) and Benjamin Stewart (IDOS) in their roles of project coordinators and project manager. The opening was followed by the signing of a Memorandum of Understanding between the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) and the Instituto Mora, following and sustaining the institutions' joint leadership in the project and their collaboration in organizing the conference. In their laudation, representatives from both institutions highlighted the importance of acting towards sustainability on the local, national, and international level while countering prevailing inequalities.

Attending this event, Pablo Enrique Yanes Rizo, Mexico City's Secretary of Education, Science, Technology and Innovation, took the opportunity to speak about the transformative nature of digital developments and to emphasize that the societal and economic dimensions of these developments may exacerbate inequalities if not carefully managed. The Secretary also described Mexico City's dedication to leveraging digitalisation in the service of citizens and to ensuring equitable internet access through a free, city-wide wireless network.

The conference participants then continued to explore and share what they had learned from their own work with the PRODIGEES project. A wide set of conference sessions covered topics like information governance; digitalisation in science, the public sector, urban planning, and finance; and the environmental impact of AI. Reflective exchanges between participants took place through a range of interactive formats. These included a world café, where everyone could speak from their own contextual perspectives; a bar camp, where people even got the chance to impersonate machines; and a gallery walk, during which the participants discussed their impressions of paintings that addressed questions of sustainability and digitalisation. These formats inspired creativity and countered exhaustion; at the same time, they offered the opportunity to learn about each other's work and share knowledge, so that participants could find many intersections and areas for potential collaborations.

The exchanges also produced several central themes. One of them was the centrality of ethically and responsibly adopting new technological tools and artificial intelligence applications for local contexts and needs, especially in important areas like education and healthcare. Further, the conference participants also agreed that the development of a public and local digital infrastructure was particularly necessary, outside of, but also within governance institutions.

The same was the case for the allocation of public and private funding that could enable this process. A significant challenge that attendees identified was how to centre human experiences and people's needs in all these contexts, which demands that equitable and sustainable technological advancements focus on citizens not as passive consumers of technologies but as powerful agents. This insight was closely tied to the urgency of bridging the gap between those who develop and those who consume digital technologies and AI, which resonated in many of the discussions. As many participants concluded, good regulation, which ensure technologies work for people and not the other way around, are crucially needed for achieving these goals.

Both project results and conference discussions showed that the topic of sustainability often falls short in digitalisation processes and ought to be put more centre stage. In this context, sustainability could have diverse meanings such as the longevity of developmental efforts, the stability of technological applications, and the reduction of environmental impacts. A highlight of the conference in this regard was the group's visit to MTP's premium data centre in Santa Fe, a major data centre in Mexico City. There, the group had the chance to learn how data storage and processing works, experiencing the physical infrastructure that made tangible the socio-technical developments previously discussed. Not only could conference participants learn about cooling systems, data centre security and electricity backups, the appropriate server temperature (18-27° Celcius), and kilowatts per rack (8-15), but they could also witness the material demands (and environmental toll) of often abstract and obscure digital technologies first-hand.

On top of these many substantive exchanges, the conference bore ample opportunities to share one's personal experiences with PRODIGEES or its related MGG programme. Many of the conference participants had been PRODIGEES researchers and conducted field research with other participating institutions. These exchanges had taken place throughout a total of 74 secondments. In addition, many other conference attendees had formerly participated in IDOS' Managing Global Governance (MGG) Academy. Aside from a surprising lack in digitalisation that international visitors had reportedly encountered in Germany, participants' overall experiences underlined the need to create strong bonds not only between institutions in the so called "Global North" and "Global South", but also within these country groups. Likewise, there still seemed to be room for improvement in the equity of the funding distribution among institutions and in the alleviation of bureaucratic hurdles.

Aligned with sustainability as a central mission to the programme, everyone finally joined forces to close the project with the aspiration to continue the growth and stabilization of the vibrant community of researchers and practitioners that had been built. Consensus shared amongst everyone at the conference was that this has only been the start of important collective work to be continued and deepened. As a first step in this direction, the group came together to identify future directions for research and collaboration which were centred around 4 major areas: 1. geopolitics, 2. environmental and natural resource protection, 3. artificial intelligence, and 4. inequality and inclusive digitalisation. Here, attendees already discovered future possibilities, both in terms of content and of suitable personal collaborations. Thus, all participants could end their reflection and exchange with a motivated and hopeful outlook.

However, the conference continued for the PRODIGEES Steering Committee, who convened the following day at Instituto Mora to discuss the longevity of digitalisation and sustainability studies within the consortium. With secondments ended, the project is set to deliver reports detailing the outcomes of the research projects—the publications, digital knowledge products, and presentations. One of the reports, the "Joint R&I Agenda and Action Plan for Improved and Continuous Cooperation", is a roadmap, building on the priority areas of digitalisation research by participants and agreed upon by the Steering Committee Members, who expressed deep interest in continuing collaboration in the field of digitalisation and sustainable development. One element that will bind the consortium beyond the lifetime of PRODIGEES is a book, a compilation of research papers from PRODIGEES researchers that is being edited by Dr. Wulf Reiners, co-coordinator of the PRODIGEES project from IDOS, and Dr. Simone Lucatello from Instituto Mora, who performed five months of secondment research in the project. Results are expected to be published in 2026.

Overall, the MGG/PRODIGEES Final conference received highly positive feedback from participants - with 75% of attendees fully endorsing it and 25% satisfied with its quality. Regarding knowledge gained, most participants (87%) felt they deepened their understanding of the link between digitalisation and sustainable development, and 87% of participants agreed that they particularly improved their insights into the Mexican context. The event successfully fostered shared perspectives on digitalisation and sustainability challenges (69%) and provided valuable exposure to innovative solutions (81%). Cultural and networking activities were widely appreciated (88%), and the venue at Instituto Mora was overwhelmingly praised (94%). Importantly, all participants felt a stronger connection to the MGG/PRODIGEES network (100%), and remained motivated to stay engaged.

Sunday, 9 March

11.00 am

Cultural Networking Programme (by bus, with stops)

Historical Centre of Mexico City

Monday, 10 March

9.30 - 10:45 am

Welcome to the MGG/PRODIGEES Final Conference

- Dr Carlos Domingues (MORA)
- Dr Wulf Reiners (IDOS)
- Benjamin Stewart (IDOS)

Monday, 10 March

9.30 - 10:45 am

MoU Ceremony & Opening Remarks

- Dr Gabriela Sánchez Gutiérrez (MORA)
- Dr Sven Grimm (IDOS)
- Dr Clarissa Heisig (German Embassy Mexico City)

11.00 - 12.30 am

Public Keynote Address

- Pablo Enrique Yanes Rizo (Secretary of Education, Science, Technology and Innovation in Mexico City)

First responses:

- Dr Sven Grimm (IDOS)
- Dr Carlos Dominguez (MORA)
- Prof Dr Willem Fourie (SU)

Moderation: Dr Simone Lucatello (MORA)

Monday, 10 March

2.15 – 3.45 pm

The Impact of MGG/PRODIGEES

- Dr Elena Bruni (LUISS)
- Dr Alessia Chiriatti, Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI)
- Dr Roberto Costa de Pimenta (FGV EBAPE)
- Dr Carlos Domínguez (MORA)
- Dr Medelina Hendytio (CSIS)
- Prof Dr Ingrid Schneider (University of Hamburg)

Moderator: Dr Sven Grimm (IDOS)

4.00 – 5.30 pm

Gallery Conversation: Talking & Walking Sustainable Digitalisation

Design and Instructions: Matthias Kachelmann (IDOS)

Tuesday, 11 March

9.30 – 9.45 am

Setting the Scene for the Parallel Workshops

- Benjamin Stewart (IDOS)
- Dr. Wulf Reiners (IDOS)

9.45 – 11.00 am

Parallel Workshops: Governance & Society

- **MGG as a digitally-enhanced Network to counter Polarisation:** Vy Dang, Eva Lynders (IDOS).
- **Social media Platforms and (global) information Governance:** Dr Anita Breuer (IDOS), Prof Dr Ingrid Schneider, Laura Fichtner (University of Hamburg).
- **Digitalisation in the Public Sector:** Arun Sharma (WB), David Bates (Visor Urbano), Dr. Sven Grimm (IDOS), Prof. Dr. Willem Fourie (Stellenbosch University).

Tuesday, 11 March

11.15 am – 12.30 pm

Parallel Workshops: Economy & Environment

- **Trends in the Digital Economy and Central Banks' Digital Currencies:** Nicola Bilotta (Florence School of Banking and Finance), Jonathan Dries (LUISS), Adinova Fauri (CSIS), Dr. Tuhinshubra Giri (Christ University), Dandy Rafitrandi (CSIS).
- **Urban Mobility, Planning, and Smart Cities:** Franco Juaregui (IDOS), Dr Isela Orihuela, Dr Mateo Crossa (MORA), Raquel Silva de Oliveira (NOMMON).
- **Environmental Impacts of Digitalisation and AI:** Prof Dr Leanne Seeliger (Stellenbosch University), Dr Simone Lucatello (MORA).

1.30 – 5.30 pm

Excursion MTP Data Center Santa Fe (bus transfer, visit, discussion)

Wednesday, 12 March

9.30 – 11.00 am

PRODIGEES Past and Future

- Dr Wulf Reiners (IDOS)
- Dr Carlos Dominguez (MORA)

11.30 am – 1.00 pm

Bar Camp / Open Space

Participants create the agenda
Facilitation: Jacqueline Aguilar (Ministry of Education), André Chusyd (Aizik International) and Juan Carlos Mendoza (GIZ Mexico)

PRODIGEES Edited Volume

- Dr Simone Lucatello (MORA)
- Dr Wulf Reiners (IDOS)

Wednesday, 12 March

2.30 – 4.00 pm

Artificial Intelligence – Challenges and Opportunities

- Dr Claudia Jiménez (Tecnológico de Monterrey & Crea con IA)

Moderation: Prof Dr Ingrid Schneider

4.15 – 5.30 pm

Closing of Conference: Reflection and Evaluation

- Dr Carlos Domínguez (MORA)
- Dr Wulf Reiners (IDOS)
- Benjamin Stewart (IDOS)

Thursday, 13 March [for PRODIGEES Steering Committee / Advisory Board only]

10.00 am – 12.30 pm

PRODIGEES Steering Committee & Advisory Board Meeting

PARTICIPANTS LIST

Participants list

Last Name	First Name	Institutional Affiliation	Country
Aguilar Baca	Jacqueline	Ministry of Education	Mexico
Arellano-Esparza	Carlos	Universidad Autónoma de Zacatecas	Mexico
Ayala Martínez	Citlali	Instituto Mora (MORA)	Mexico
Bates	David	Visor Urbano	Mexico
Becerra Monroy	Cristian	Voluntad Organizada	Mexico
Becerril	Malinali	WomenTechMakers México	Mexico
Berthier	Bruno	Pintando Futuros	Mexico
Bilotta	Nicola	Florence School of Banking and Finance	Italy
Brand Rivas y Taboada	Jonathan Immanuel	German Embassy Mexico City	Mexico
Breuer	Anita	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)	Germany
Bruni	Elena	Luiss Guido Carli University (LUISS)	Italy
Ceccon Rocha	Brisa	Wikimedia Foundation	Mexico
Chavez Becker	Carlos	Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana	Mexico
Chiriatti	Alessia	Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI)	Italy
Chusyd	André	INCO Academy	Brazil
Crossa	Mateo	Instituto Mora (MORA)	Mexico
Cruz	Neydi	Instituto Mora (MORA)	Mexico
da Costa Pimenta	Roberto	Fundação Getúlio Vargas (FGV)	Brazil
de Diego	Lilia	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ)	Mexico
Dominguez	Juan Carlos	Instituto Mora (MORA)	Mexico
Dries	Jonathan	Luiss Guido Carli University (LUISS)	Italy
Fauri	Adinova	Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS)	Indonesia
Fichtner	Laura	University of Hamburg	USA
Fourie	Willem	Stellenbosch University	South Africa
Galvez Muñoz	Irais Daniela	Google Cloud	Mexico
García Luna Gonzalez	Deborah	Voluntad Organizada	Mexico
Gómez García	Bianca Elena	Instituto Mora (MORA)	Mexico
Giri	Tuhinubhra	Christ University	India

Grimm	Sven	German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS)	Germany
Gutierrez	Teresa	Mexicano Primero	Mexico
Haegle	Ramona	Julius-Maximilians-University Würzburg	Germany
Heisig	Clarissa	German Embassy Mexico City	Mexico
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Kumar	Amit	Research Information System for Developing Countries (RIS)	India
Kusharwanti Hendytio	Medelina	Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS)	Indonesia
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Martínez	Alberto	El Colegio de México	Mexico
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Mendoza Enriquez	Olivia Andrea	Centro de Investigación y Docencia Económicas (CIDE)	Mexico
Mendoza Reyes	Juan Carlos	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ)	Mexico
Mulaudzi	Khuselwa Faith	Department of Basic Education	South Africa
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Sharma	Arun	World Bank	India
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Silva de Oliveira	Raquel	NOMMON	Brazil
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MGG / PRODIGEES | Digitalisation Towards Sustainable Development

Ciencia y Tecnología
Secretaría de Ciencia, Humanidades, Tecnología e Innovación

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